

CUSTOMER COMPLAINTS ARE IMPORTANT FOR BUSINESS GROWTH

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Abstract

Complaints should be considered as an indicator of organizational performance assessment, signaling problems or failures in internal processes that need quick recovery to avoid migration of profitable customers. Organizations must learn that the consequences of losing customers are both profit decrease and negative word of mouth. The aim of the present study is to highlight the key features of an effective complaint management process, as a less expensive system of diagnosing and learning a company's weaknesses. Results focus on customer complaining behavior and subsequently on the development and implementation of the service recovery strategy. Various issues or difficulties that sometimes are beyond the control of the business, lead to customers' dissatisfaction. A customer complaint is a way by which customers express their dissatisfaction. With the quick growth of technology and the abundance of convenient channels for customers to voice their complaints, like chatbots, email, and the web, online complaints have increased dramatically. As a result, handling customers' complaints quickly and efficiently became challenging.

INTRODUCTION

Although complaints from customers may seem to reflect poorly on the brand, they are really loaded with beneficial information that can be used to the company's advantage whenever customers make negative comments about your goods or services. As soon as you can, use your knowledge to address specific customer problems. It would be beneficial to deliver top-notch customer service while also upholding a strong brand reputation in the sector. On the other side, when handled properly, negative comments can occasionally be helpful. Consider that by forgoing the expense of conducting a customer satisfaction survey on your end, your business is obtaining free customer insights and priceless information.

This paper focuses on the complaints related to Indian Banking sector. As per the classical definition "A Bank accepts deposit for the purpose of Lending". Being the sensitive area related to common-man's money; it is highly important for Banks to ensure high standards of customer service. Here we discuss the points related to concerns of customers they have with the Banks and try to understand areas of improvements which will strengthen the banking system and ensure sustainable growth for Indian banks.

Banking industry is now more competitive than ever; therefore, banks require an efficient grievance handling system for their customers. Although, there is already a system in place for customer 's grievance handling set up by individual Banks' and the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) also. But at the ground the banks need to step up and improve their processes and working style to ensure optimum customer satisfaction with sustainable business growth.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To build consumer confidence and trust is very important for banking organizations and even more important is to maintain that confidence and trust. In today 's competitive era you cannot think of an industry which is providing variety of services but no customer complaint is there.

Complaints/ grievance are the regular problem of the service industry specially the banking industry but the challenge is to swiftly copewith that problem and provide a hassle-free system of grievance handling to your customers to sustain them for a long time. And this task is impossible for banks if they do not have an effective consumer grievance redressal system.

According to Kolekar (2016), customer dispute resolution is an important part of customer satisfaction and the commencement of the Banking Ombudsman Scheme by the Reserve Bank of India is a laudable step in this direction. Mishra also states that, The Ombudsman scheme is a boon and a very important channel for redressal of grievances by the public against banks and banking services.

It is framed in such a manner that it does not oust the jurisdiction of other courts, and hence, aggrieved people do not hesitate in using the banking ombudsman as a primary forum for resolution of disputes regarding banks.

As per Saxena and Kaur (2018), for an organization to be responsive, accountable, and accessible, an effectual and effective grievance redressal system is of paramount (Volume-04, Issue-04, April-2019 RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary RRIJM 2015, All Rights Reserved 1143 | Page importance).

Thus, it has become significant for banks to render grievance free services to their customers to gain competitive advantage in terms of customer satisfaction and customer retention.

Organizations that invest the time, energy, and resources required to achieve excellence in customer service will be the ones that will thrive and grow. As the range and volume of banking services has grown, year after year, the public has expressed its dissatisfaction with the poor quality of service or the denial of service.

This situation leads to creation of grievance redressal system in a timely and inexpensive manner.

As per an article published by Tapestry Networks.com, in these early days of sharper regulatory focus on consumer issues, there has been a high degree of market uncertainty and precedent-setting enforcement actions. Regulators are developing new approaches as they enhance oversight and navigate interactions among agencies with overlapping mandates.

METHODOLOGY

As the research focus Indian Banking system, the source of the research work is the recent annual report published by RESERVE BANK - INTEGRATED OMBUDSMAN SCHEME, 2021 dated 24th Jan 2025, for the period April 1, 2023 to March 31, 2024 under RESERVE BANK OF INDIA-CONSUMER EDUCATION AND PROTECTION DEPARTMENT, CENTRAL OFFICE, Mumbai (Maharashtra).

The Reserve Bank – Integrated Ombudsman Scheme (RB-IOS), 2021 (the Scheme) was launched on November 12, 2021, by integrating three erstwhile Ombudsman schemes viz. Banking Ombudsman Scheme (BOS), 2006, Ombudsman Scheme for Non-Banking Financial Companies (OSNBFC), 2018 and the Ombudsman Scheme for Digital Transactions (OSDT), 2019.

The Scheme is being administered by the Consumer Education and Protection Department (CEPD) of the Reserve Bank through 24 Ombudsmen offices. Currently, the Scheme covers the following regulated entities:

1. Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks, Scheduled Primary (Urban) Co-operative Banks and Non-Scheduled Primary (Urban) Co-operative Banks with deposits size of Rs 50 crore and above as on the date of the audited balance sheet of the previous financial year;
2. Non-Banking Financial Companies (excluding Housing Finance Companies) which (a) are authorized to accept deposits; or (b) have customer interface, with an assets size of Rs 100 crore and above as on the date of the audited balance sheet of the previous financial year;
3. Payment System Participants; and
4. Credit Information Companies.

In the report, RBI shared the data, pertaining to number of complaints received to ORBIO (Office of Reserve Bank of India Ombudsman) for various services in Banking domain. The report signifies the overall status of complaints under various domains in the last three F.Y.

The below mentioned data is published in the aforesaid mentioned report and it is used here strictly for the purpose of learning and understanding the relationship between customer complaints and top management of the organization. See table below –

Category wise receipt of complaints at ORBIOs			
Nature of Complaints	F.Y.2021-22\$	F.Y.2022-23	F.Y.2023-24^
Complaints against banks			
Mobile / electronic banking	39,388	39,855	54,364
	14.69%	20.27%	22.48%
Loans and Advances	24,507	39,579	54,336
	9.14%	20.13%	22.47%
Opening/Operation of Deposit accounts	16,388	33,612	46,315
	6.11%	17.09%	19.15%
Credit Cards	32,162	24,549	33,198
	12.00%	12.48%	13.73%
ATM /CDM/ Debit Cards	41,375	28,635	25,173
	15.43%	14.56%	10.41%
Pension related	6,179	4,377	4,104
	2.30%	2.23%	1.70%
Remittances and Collection of instruments	3,235	2,937	4,099
	1.21%	1.49%	1.69%
Para-banking	1,480	2,476	4,368
	0.55%	1.26%	1.81%
Notes and Coins	296	505	537
	0.11%	0.26%	0.22%
Other products and services	1,03,075	20,110	15,337
	38.45%	10.23%	6.34%
Total (Banks)	2,68,085	1,96,635	2,41,831
Complaints against NBFCs			
Loans and Advances	18,729	18,657	27,471
	56.22%	56.41%	64.34%
Other products and services	14,585	14,415	15,228
	43.78%	43.59%	35.66%
Total (NBFCs)	33,314	33,072	42,699
Complaints against PSOs/PSPs			
Mobile / electronic banking	2,160	2,246	2,825
	69.74%	64.99%	57.77%
Other products and services	937	1,210	2,065
	30.26%	35.01%	42.23%
Total (PSOs/PSPs)	3,097	3,456	4,890
Complaints against Credit Information Companies			
Loans and advances	-	754	3,180
	-	72.57%	82.66%
Credit Cards	-	63	185
	-	6.06%	4.81%
Other products and services	-	222	482
	-	21.37%	12.53%
Total (CICs)	-	1,039	3,847
\$ Data pertains to complaints received during the year under BOS, OSNBFC, OSDT and RB-IOs, 2021.			
^ 657 complaints pertain to entities not covered under (RB-IOs) 2021. Details of these complaints are provided in Appendix 1.5.			
Note: The data for the year 2021-22 is not strictly comparable due to structural changes in the Ombudsman framework of RBI w.e.f. November 12, 2021.			

RESULT

What Do Customers Actually Complain About?

The difference between what customers receives and the products and services that companies offer is what are referred to as the “customer complaint” difference. The offerings made by a brand and the interactions customers have with that brand are all in conflict. Customers frequently complain about brands when their expectations are not met by the products or services, they receive from them.

If we analyse data mentioned in the above table, there is growth in number of complaints received Y-O-Y basis specifically in the 3 major areas viz., Mobile/Internet Banking, Loans/Advances and Opening or Operations of Deposit Accounts. This data indicates that majority of the customers visit / contact Banks for these services. Also, these three parameters are the major contributor in Bank’s overall business. If Banks pay attention to improve upon these parameters, it will be beneficial for overall growth of business for banks, as this will not only increase the Banks’ operational efficiency but also enhance customer experience.

A brand can rapidly resolve a complaint and make a beneficial adjustment, depending on the nature of the complaint. As an alternative, a business could change that feature or service for the benefit of its customers.

There Are Numerous Customer Complaint Categories That Are Based On:

- Poor Service Quality at Bank’s service outlets
- Ineffective Brand Communication by the Bank
- Promises Breached by the Bank

Customer Complaint Types

1. Product Criticisms

Product complaints occur when customers are dissatisfied with their purchases and seek company’s assistance in resolving them. Product complaints might take several forms depending on the company’s strategy, but it always involves defects or operational difficulties. If a product is merely defective, the firm should either refund or replace it. If a customer is having difficulty using or understanding any product, answering questions and offering help will typically resolve the problem. For example, internet banking product of a Bank is not working properly despite having no technical problems at customers’ end. This is may arise due to some design issues in the software or hardware issues from Bank’s side.

Product troubles are widespread in that any organization may anticipate the occurrence of a breakage or technological difficulty. But persistent product difficulties may indicate that the organization needs to investigate why they are occurring and take corrective action.

2. Complaints about Customer Service

When a customer has an unpleasant or failed encounter with a member of the business, a customer service complaint occurs. While the complaint may be directed at a customer service agent, it might also be directed at a sales representative, administrator, or any other employee that interacts with the public and customers. Customers who file these complaints typically believe that the firm did not appreciate their business or that the employees did not treat them nicely. In case of Banks, this situation arises mostly during the operations related to saving accounts/ current account along with related services like opening / operating lockers in banks, updating customer details in existing accounts, etc.

If the customer has to wait for assistance, they may complain about the pace of customer care. It might be useful to keep track of these complaints. The greatest solution might be found by noting the employee or other source of customer service problems. In certain situations, company could decide to reassess how to deliver customer support, meet with the team member who is the target of the complaint, or both.

3. Value Issues

Customers complain about value when they believe that company's products pricing is excessive. These complaints reflect in many cases where a customer begins their complaint by referencing the money or effort they put into your services and ends by stressing their dissatisfaction with the outcomes. For example, customers are having problem with interest rates charged by various banks on the loans and advances. This also includes, various processing fees and related charges which are hidden at the time of enquiry about the any loan product.

Value complaints must be thoroughly considered so that your organization can determine whether it has to change its product or better manage customers' expectations.

4. Complaints from New Customers

When someone buys the product for the first time and is dissatisfied, they may have a new customer complaint that they would like to share with company. These criticisms are frequently comparison-based. The new customers are contrasting their experience with either what company promoted or with what they get when they shop at your rivals. Some new customers could dislike company's particular item, or perhaps they had a bad experience with it when they first encountered it.

For instance, a customer will compare the service response of the various banks. There also chances of false commitments like enhanced feature of Bank's Credit Cards from bank side to increase sales of their card business.

5. Customers' Repeated Complaints

Recurring customer complaints are those that a company hear from its frequent customers. These complaints are especially important since their causes are frequently easy to detect. The company understands that repeat customers typically like and value

company's services. As a result, when people complain, the company can be certain that something precisely relevant to their experience on this occasion went wrong. These customers are uniquely suited to tell how or why they experienced an issue since they are familiar with the organization.

Repeat customers are critical to the profitability and long-term success of any firm. When they share a complaint, the firm can usually be certain that the customer plans to return, which is why it's critical to resolve issues that emerged during the transactions.

6. Complaints That Continue

Customers who constantly exchange critiques generate chronic complaints. Even though they are regular customers, some customers believe it is necessary to continuously mention how company's business might improve. If a company built a relationship with a customer who often complains, it's critical that the firm should listen to what they have to say. But the company should be aware that these customers are unlikely to change their opinion of the organization. It might be possible debate the issue or wait to see if anyone else raises the same issue before making any radical adjustments.

DISCUSSION

The Advantages of Customer Complaint for The Business

Verify what customers think about a company's products and services by reviewing customer complaints. Instead of doing surveys and market research, classifying client complaints might help to find areas that need improvement. By adopting such innovations, businesses may provide superior customer service while maintaining a significant competitive advantage. To understand why customer complaints are vital for any business, let's discuss the following few points:

1. Improved Customer Understanding

Customers often understand the products and services that businesses can be missing. IT will be better to serve the customers by understanding their needs and concerns after reading **customer complaints**. Resolve any problems as quickly as you can, even if a customer just communicates a little dissatisfaction. Discover the psychology of the customer and how to use it to develop innovative goods and services. In the end, it results in more brand loyalty and favorable customer word-of-mouth.

2. Improving Customer Service

The reasons behind the massive rise in customer complaints about a brand can be slow response rate or general lack of participation in all forms of communication from a company's side. Companies may learn from customer complaints how to provide better customer service and how crucial it is to their reputation. To connect with all customer care touchpoints and deliver outstanding customer service, businesses use multichannel support.

3. Customer Communication Enhancements

A successful business depends heavily on customer communication, and businesses must be able to handle customers' problems. Customers could think that businesses do not value their consent, so it is up to businesses to create a sense of worth in them. Customers who have issues or complaints should be encouraged to contact brands so that they may be resolved as quickly as possible. Customers must understand that businesses care about solving their problems since doing so will increase customer loyalty and brand reputation.

4. Increased Customer Loyalty

Most customers who report a problem to a business do so in the hope of getting their concerns resolved quickly or getting compensation. Make sure the customer support representative answers call quickly and offers appropriate solutions on time. Even if the customer's problem cannot be resolved, making up for the loss in some other way will improve the reputation of your business. No matter how difficult they are, it will motivate customers to support your business moving forward.

5. Error Recognition

There is a chance that hundreds of other customers have the same issues but haven't approached the company. It is essential to thoroughly examine each customer complaint, particularly if multiple customers have raised it.

The company can tackle problems that were previously unaware of by looking into the challenges and concerns that are affecting business. One should work to improve company's operations and services and fix any flaws in products and services to have a strong brand and be successful.

6. Increased Positive Word-Of-Mouth

For a brand to ensure customer satisfaction, it is important to determine immediate needs and solve any issues with product offerings. If a company responds quickly to its customers' problems, customers will recommend it to their friends and relatives.

Customers' impressions of a brand are strongly influenced by the level of customer service provided. References from trustworthy family and friends are valuable and far stronger than any form of advertising.

The likelihood that a potential client will become one rises when they hear positive things about a business. This shows how crucial customer complaints are to the success of company / brand.

So, before reaching to the conclusion, let us try to understand the impact of customer complaints with respect to the business growth of Banks in India.

Reserve Bank of India in its report dated June 04, 2024 **Credit by Scheduled Commercial Banks – March 2024 (Annual BSR-1)** highlighted the below points: -

- ❖ Bank credit growth (y-o-y) increased by 15.3 per cent, net of merger⁴ (19.1 per cent including the merger impact) during 2023-24 as compared to 15.8 per cent rise in the previous financial year.
- ❖ During 2023-24, all major activities recorded double digit growth in bank credit.
- ❖ Private sector banks recorded over 15 per cent growth for the third consecutive year – their share in total credit by SCBs rose to 40.6 per cent in March 2024 from 33.4 per cent five years ago and 19.4 per cent ten years ago; the corresponding share of public sector banks declined to 51.8 per cent from 73.2 per cent ten years ago.
- ❖ With general rise in interest rates, the share of loans bearing over 9 per cent interest rate increased to 57.8 per cent of total bank loans in March 2024 as compared with 56.1 per cent share a year ago and 31.4 per cent two years ago.

In the second report of RBI dated June 04, 2024 **Deposits with Scheduled Commercial Banks - March 2024 (Annual BSR-2)** highlighted the below points-

- ❖ Bank deposits increased (y-o-y) by 13.0 per cent, net of merger (13.5 per cent including the impact of merger) during 2023-24 as compared to 10.2 per cent growth in the previous year; deposits of all population groups (*viz.*, rural, semi-urban, urban, and metropolitan) accelerated in the latest year.
- ❖ Current, savings and term deposits accounted for 9.8 per cent, 30.8 per cent and 59.4 per cent, respectively, of total deposits in March 2024.
- ❖ During 2023-24, 79.1 per cent of the rise in term deposits were mobilized in the maturity bucket of one to three years; this category accounted for nearly two thirds of outstanding term deposits at year-end.

CONCLUSION

It is evident from the business data of RBI that despite having risen in the complaints, there is a sustainable business growth in Banking industry. Therefore, if complaints are been paid attention it will ensure strong banking system and overall enhanced customer experience which will lead to better profitability.

Lastly, a company has to understand that responding to customer issues is a major element of doing business. A business cannot satisfy every customer owing to various commercial and financial constraints.

An essential action a business may take is to identify and respond to customer issues. Make the most of it by taking what you've learned from it and using it to enhance any facets of the goods or services associated with your brand. Although businesses must find answers to the challenges in order to increase business success, customers' complaints demand patience and time to address.

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References

- 1) Dr. Deepika Singh Tomar Amity Business School, Amity University Madhya Pradesh, Maharajpura Dang, Gwalior (MP) (India). Volume-04 ISSN: 2455-3085 (Online) Issue-04 RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary April -2019 www.rrjournals.com [UGC Listed Journal]
- 2) Annual Report on Banking Ombudsman Scheme, 2015-16 (2016). Retrieved from <https://rbi.org.in/Scripts/PublicationsView.aspx?id=17399>
- 3) C Ram Gopal (2014), Management of Financial Services, Vikas Publishing, New Delhi.
- 4) file:///E:/Papers%20in%20progress/Banking%20Paper/Importance%20Of%20Customer%20Service%20In%20The%20Banking%20Industry%20Marketing%20Essay.html
- 5) file:///E:/Papers%20in%20progress/Banking%20Paper/grievance-redressal-policy-for-the-year-2016-17%20(1).pdf
- 6) https://www.tapestrynetworks.com/sites/default/files/publication_pdf/BGLN%20ViewPoints%20%20Leading%20the%20digital%20transformation%20of%20banking%20-%206%20August%20-%20FINAL%20LTR%20-%20web.pdf
- 7) Kolekar Y (2016). Role of Banking Ombudsman in Banking Reforms. https://mpr.aub.unimuenchen.de/75660/1/MPRA_paper_75660.pdf
- 8) Pragya Mishra, A Brief Analysis of the Banking Ombudsman Scheme in India, <http://www.manupatrafast.com>.
- 9) Saxena C & Kaur V (2018). Identification of Limiting factors of Customer Complaint Redressal System of Banks: A Study of Banks of Punjab from Bankers 'Perspective. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, 6 (2), 583-87.
- 10) Sharma AK (2016), Banks Widen Complaint Redressal System. Retrieved from <https://www.livemint.com/Money/hP08ycT8FGFGE1gZRwQFrO/Banks-widen-complaint-redressalsystem.htm>
- 11) Reserve Bank of India Press Release: 2024-2025/440, dated 04th June 2024
- 12) Reserve Bank of India Press Release: 2024-2025/439, dated 04th June 2024